

**Formative Assessment to Support Literacy and Numeracy
Development at Primary and Post-primary Levels**

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Author Note

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The views expressed in this report are those of the authors, and not their institutions.

Summary

Despite over two decades of intensive research on the implementation of formative assessment practices in classrooms, and on the effects of such assessment on students' learning and motivation, there is, as yet, no universally-accepted definition, with different researchers defining formative assessment as it relates to their studies. A common understanding is that, when goals are clear and measurable for teachers and students, assessment data can provide feedback on progress with regard to those goals. It is also generally recognised that data can be based on instruments (for example, tests or performances), or on the skilled observations of teachers (sometimes referred to as "process"), or on some combination of the two.

Results of studies that have sought to quantify the effects of formative assessment on student achievement are mixed. While earlier studies (those published before 2000) reported large effect sizes for formative assessment, more recent reviews, which have implemented stronger quality criteria for the selection of studies, have reported more modest effects. Across students, effect sizes are generally larger for literacy and mathematics compared with other subjects (e.g., Klute et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2020). The outcomes for studies providing feedback in electronic format have also been mixed. Although one comprehensive meta-analysis identified "promising evidence" that digitally-delivered formative assessment could facilitate learning of aspects of literacy (basic reading skills, aspects of spelling and grammar) and mathematics, the authors (See et al., 2021) conclude that formative assessment with technology was no more effective than formative assessment without technology. Such findings reflect a shortage of well-designed studies that can identify the effects of formative digital assessment. *A key finding across many studies on digital and non-digital formative assessment is that it is most effective when conceptualised as an integrated element of instruction in environments where teachers and students are jointly responsible for learning* (e.g., Heitink et al., 2016; Schildkamp et al., 2020) .

The research on the effects of formative assessment has also identified factors associated with the successful implementation of such assessment. These include the source of feedback (including peer- and self-assessment), quality of feedback, the use of learning trajectories or learning pathways as a basis for assessing students, the impact of tasks that reveal students' thinking, and the pedagogical content knowledge of teachers and their professional development.

In general, all forms of feedback are effective but self-assessment and, to a slightly lesser extent, peer-assessment have a significant impact on learning (e.g., Andrade, 2019; Double et al., 2019). In general, the assignment of a grade by a peer is not recommended for primary or post-primary students. On the other hand, self-grading is found to be effective, probably because it promotes metacognition and self-regulation on the part of students (Sanchez et al., 2017). Feedback appears to be most effective when it is clear, task-related and encouraging of student effort (Hodgen et al., 2018). It can focus on achievement, effort or process. There is evidence that process feedback with a focus on strategies to bridge the gap between where students are and where they need to be is particularly valuable (Schildkamp et al., 2020). According to Van der Kleij et al. (2015), elaborated feedback, described as feedback that provides an explanation, is more effective than providing the correct answer and considerably more effective than indicating whether an answer is correct or not. Furthermore, they found that the immediacy of feedback, especially on digital devices, was beneficial to student learning, though delayed feedback was identified as useful for more challenging or higher-order tasks.

There is some evidence that learning trajectories/pathways can provide a good basis for formative assessment, with significant development work done in mathematics, and, to a lesser extent, in literacy (Calkins et al., 2019; Hodgen, et al., 2020). In the case of writing, it has been suggested that student-facing checklists based on trajectories can support students to self-assess and set goals. The use of learning trajectories as part of the design of technological assessment holds some promise as this allows for adaptive feedback. Revelatory tasks – tasks which reveal student thinking - have potential in this regard as they allow teachers to garner insight into students' knowledge and misconceptions and also their disposition to the subject(s) involved and their motivation to engage (e.g., Burkhardt and Schoenfeld, 2019; Dooley et al., 2014; Kennedy et al., 2012). Teachers can gather data as appropriate from students' engagement in these tasks as evidentiary warrants, for example, portfolios, work samples, audio recordings and photographs. Such data can also emanate from other curricular subjects, such as an integrated project that might make demands of a student's literacy and/or numeracy skills.

In providing feedback to students, teachers need to decide whether immediate feedback is required, and, if so, the nature of that feedback.. They also need a knowledge of students' misconceptions in literacy and numeracy and the pedagogical strategies that

might help to address these misconceptions (Burkhardt and Schoenfeld, 2019; Van der Kleij et al., 2015) . An understanding of learning trajectories/pathways in order to design appropriate learning tasks and extend students' thinking is also required. This entails the development of teachers' pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) relevant to literacy and numeracy as well as an understanding and knowledge of formal and informal assessment processes (Schildkamp et al., 2020). A key finding is that the relevant professional development should extend over a considerable period of time and involve expert support in order to benefit teachers' practices in formative assessment (Lane et al., 2019; Lysaght & O'Leary, 2013, 2017).

Finally, school leaders can play an important role in supporting teachers' use of formative assessment, and the strategies they use to provide effective feedback to students (Lane et al., 2019; Newman et al., 2021). The research indicates, not surprisingly, that school leaders with responsibility for formative assessment should be knowledgeable about its purposes, and be able to provide a rationale for its use, as well as a non-threatening environment where effective use of assessment data, in all its forms, is modelled for teachers. It is also clear that decentralised organisational structures at school level, and distributed leadership are conducive to implementation of formative assessment, and to ensuring accountability pressures on teachers do not lead to unintended impacts on instructional and assessment processes. The research also indicates that the development of feedback policy at school level should offer suggestions and exemplars for making feedback more manageable, but that specific methods and features of feedback should be decided by teachers, based on their professional judgements about students' learning (Education Endowment Foundation, 2021).

Recommendations

Pillar 2: Teachers' and Early Childhood Care and Education practitioners' professional practice

Teachers need to develop an understanding of the different approaches to formative assessment such as data-based decision making drawing on the outcomes of tests, performance-based assessments, curriculum-embedded assessments, structured observations, alongside minute-to-minute ongoing assessment in the classroom, and how these types of formative assessment can meet different educational goals. (Schildkamp et al., 2020; Sparks, 2015; Wiliam, 2016)

High levels of intensive and sustained professional development (PD) in formative assessment in literacy and numeracy should be available to primary and post-primary teachers. This PD should focus on teachers' pedagogical content knowledge, assessment literacy and data literacy, and should have onsite components. (Lane et al., 2019; Schildkamp et al., 2020; Lysaght & O'Leary, 2017)

Teachers should be supported to use learning trajectories in literacy and numeracy as part of their formative assessment practices. (Calkins et al., 2019; Hodgen et al., 2020)

Teachers should collaborate to design tasks that are suitable for revealing students' thinking, sense-making and and misconceptions in literacy and numeracy. (Burkhardt & Schoenfeld, 2019; McDonald & Smith, 2020; Traga-Philippakos & Moore, 2020)

Pillar 3: Building the capacity of early years/school leadership

School leaders with responsibility for assessment in literacy and numeracy should be knowledgeable about the purposes and rationale of formative assessment, and provide a non-threatening environment where effective use of assessment data, in all its forms, can be modelled. (Lane et al., 2019)

Where the provision of professional development in formative assessment of literacy and numeracy is concerned, school leaders should ensure that teachers have regular and protected meeting time for meaningful examination of assessment practice and preparation of assessment tools, feedback and instructional response. Professional learning should be sustained, collaborative, work-embedded and situated within school needs. (Lane et al., 2019)

Decentralised organisational structures at school level, and distributed leadership are recommended for formative assessment in literacy and numeracy to ensure that accountability pressure on teachers does not lead to unintended impacts on teaching and assessment processes. (Lane et al., 2019)

School-level policy on feedback in the areas of literacy and numeracy should offer suggestions on making feedback more manageable, and provide detailed examples, but specific methods and features of feedback should be decided by teachers themselves, thereby supporting their autonomy to exercise evidence-informed professional judgements. (Education Endowment Foundation, 2021)

Pillar 4: Curriculum and the learning experience

Formative assessment should be an integrated element of literacy and numeracy instruction, with teachers and students jointly responsible for the quality of teaching and learning in classrooms. There should be an emphasis on interaction between teachers, students and their peers in order to facilitate formative assessment. (Heitink et al., 2016; Schildkamp et al., 2020)

Tasks that reveal students' thinking in literacy and numeracy should be incorporated into the learning experience, e.g., writing for learning; portfolios (including e-portfolios); running records of reading; documentation of talk; mathematical problem-solving and problem posing; mathematical concept maps; diagrams. (Burkhardt and Schoenfeld, 2019; Graham et al., 2020; Hartmeyer et al., 2017; Hodgen et al., 2020; McDonald & Smith, 2020; Traga-Philippakos and Moore, 2020; Wang et al., 2020)

Pillar 5: Students with Additional Learning Needs

Digital assessment tools that provide adaptive assignments in literacy and numeracy to students based on their previous assessed performance are recommended as part of a broader learning experience for those with additional learning needs. (Lane et al., 2019; See et al., 2021)

Pillar 6: Assessment and evaluation to support learning in literacy and numeracy

In general, feedback on literacy and numeracy tasks should be elaborated, that is, it should be accompanied by an explanation. In particular, feedback should be aimed at strategies that bridge the gap between where students are and where they need to be, while promoting metacognition and self-regulated learning. (Hodgen et al., 2018; Schildkamp et al., 2020; Van der Kleij et al., 2015)

Opportunities for self- and peer-assessment in literacy and numeracy should be identified by teachers and incorporated into the learning process. Criteria for such assessment should be concrete, task-specific, and graduated, and should be developed in conjunction with students. Support should be provided to younger children to engage in the processes of self- and peer-assessment. Where appropriate, students should engage in self-grading; however, grading by peers is not encouraged for primary or post-primary students. (Andrade, 2019; Double et al., 2019; Sanchez et al., 2017)

A range of relevant exemplars in literacy and numeracy should be made available to teachers *and* students to support them in interpreting learning trajectories and student-facing checklists. (Calkins et al., 2019; Hodgen et al., 2020)

Research on Formative Assessment

Introduction

The distinction between the summative and formative assessment was first suggested by Scriven (1967) in the context of programme evaluation. He defined summative evaluation as a judgement on the overall value of an educational programme (as compared with a different one), and viewed formative evaluation as a tool for facilitating programme improvement. Bloom (1969, p. 48) identified the purpose of formative evaluation as “providing feedback and correctives at each stage in the teaching-learning process”, and summative evaluation as describing what the learner had achieved at the end of a course or programme¹, representing a shift from programmes to students. Black and Wiliam’s (1998a, 1998b) seminal work on the impact of formative assessment on students’ learning brought the terms “formative” and “summative” into everyday use, in the context of classroom- and school-based assessment. This report focuses on formative assessment. A review of research on summative assessment is presented in a separate report.

According to Wiliam (2006), formative assessment involves collecting information or evidence about student learning, interpreting it in terms of students’ needs, and using it to alter what happens. Formative assessment can be viewed as a set of tools to be used to improve learning (for example, scoring rubrics, checklists, mastery tests) and a set of processes that are implemented in classroom settings (e.g., effective use of teacher questioning, provision of feedback that supports students in setting new learning goals). Goal-setting is a fundamental element of formative assessment. In classroom-based formative assessment, the focus is often on establishing and achieving appropriate goals for students. It has been argued that, when goals are clear and measurable for teachers and students, assessment data can provide feedback on progress with regard to those goals (Hattie & Timperley, 2007).

Despite over a decade of work on formative assessment spurred on by Black and Wiliam’s seminal articles, Bennett (2011) noted that no definitive definition was available at the time. He argues that formative assessment should be conceived as neither a test nor a process, but some thoughtful integration of process and purposefully-

¹ The terms ‘assessment of learning’ (AoL) and ‘assessment for learning’ (AfL) have also been used to denote summative and formative assessment, respectively.

designed methodology or instrumentation. As recently as 2020, Schildkamp et al. wrote that there is still no clear consensus on what formative assessment encompasses, though it is accepted as a key practice for teachers.

Despite an overall lack of consensus on what formative assessment is, researchers define it as it relates to the context of their work. For example, Spark's (2015) definition includes formative learning assessment (mainly student-led) and formative diagnostic assessment (mainly teacher-led). She describes formative learning assessment as the process of teaching students how to set goals for their learning, identify their growth towards those goals, evaluate the quality of their work, and identify strategies to improve. For her, formative diagnostic assessment involves teachers in questioning, testing or demonstrating, identifying how a student is learning and where their strengths and weaknesses lie, documenting potential strategies to improve learning, and focusing on individual growth.

Wiliam (2016) presents a different classification based on the context in which formative assessment is used:

- *Improving student achievement with instructional data teams* - setting up assessments and reviewing results in teams to identify students who are underperforming, and responding with interventions (Schildkamp et al., 2020 refer to this type of formative assessment as data-based decision making (DBDM), noting that it can comprise test results, curriculum-embedded assessments, and structured observations from daily classroom practice).²
- *Building teacher quality through classroom formative assessment* - training teachers to teach in a formative way, so that minute-to-minute in the classroom, children are exposed to ongoing formative assessment and feedback. Schildkamp et al. (2020) refer to this type of formative assessment as assessment for learning (AfL), and note that information for AfL is often gathered in a less-structured and more informal manner, and can derive from a range of different assessment sources, including observations, portfolios, practical demonstrations, paper-and-pencil tests, peer assessment, self-assessment, and dialogues. They highlight the importance of ongoing interaction between teachers and learners, during everyday classroom practice, in the form of continual dialogues and feedback loops, with immediate feedback used to guide future learning.

² Research related to DBMD is considered in the report on Summative assessment because of its focus on testing.

Wiliam (2016) notes that the two models are not mutually exclusive and both models are often implemented together in schools, though greater learning gains are associated with the classroom-based approach.

Cizek, Andrade and Bennett (2019) summarise the key characteristics of formative assessment as:

- Providing examples of learning goals including, when relevant, the specific grading criteria or rubrics that will be used to evaluate students' work;
- Requiring development of plans for attaining desired goals;
- Including frequent assessment, including student self-assessment, peer assessment, and assessment embedded within learning activities;
- Including feedback that is non-evaluative, specific, timely, related to learning goals, and provides recommendations for how to improve;
- Encouraging students to self-monitor progress toward the learning goals;
- Promoting metacognition and reflection by students on their work;
- Encouraging students to take responsibility for their own learning.

A number of challenges to the implementation of formative assessment have been identified in the literature. While acknowledging the importance of achieving a balance between formative and summative assessment in schools, the OECD (2005) notes that high-stakes summative assessments at post-primary level can be significant barriers to formative practice. To address this, they called on educational systems to implement multiple measures of student progress. They also highlight the importance of investing in training and support for formative assessment, as well as involving students and their parents in formative assessment. Atherton (2018) suggests that when formative assessment is brought in as a bolt-on solution to regular teaching, especially in high-stakes summative cultures (where there may be considerable emphasis on final examinations), it is unlikely to succeed. Instead, he argues, formative assessment must be embedded in a self-improving educational community, where space is made for continuing professional development and professional reflection.

In the Interim Report on the Literacy and Numeracy Strategy (DES, 2017), formative assessment is highlighted as a key approach to effective teaching and learning at all levels (early years, primary, post-primary). Hence, the questions that follow are designed

to gain a better understanding, through international research, of how formative assessment can best be used to promote achievement and other outcomes in literacy and numeracy, taking into account recent developments in technology.

Research Questions

The following questions underpin the current report:

1. To what extent does formative assessment, including digital formative assessment, improve students' performance in literacy and numeracy?
2. What factors are associated with effective formative assessment in literacy and numeracy?
3. What supports can facilitate the successful implementation of formative assessment in classrooms and schools?

In this report, we first look at the impact of formative assessment in general on student outcomes in literacy and numeracy, including studies involving digital technology. We examine the effects of dimensions of formative assessment that emerged through the systematic review process. These include feedback, self- and peer-assessment, learning trajectories/pathways, revelatory tasks and technology in formative assessment. Prerequisites for effective formative assessment are then considered. In the final section, we deliberate on our research questions on the basis of our findings and discuss the implications.

Relationship between Formative Assessment and Achievement

A key question in relation to formative assessment is its effect on learning. Meta-analyses of formative assessment published in the late 1990s and early 2000s suggest that it can have a strong effect on students' learning by accelerating achievement gains, promoting equity learning outcomes, and building students' 'learning to learn' skills. In particular, Black and Wiliam (1998a) report large effect sizes (between .40 and .70) for the impact of formative assessment on student achievement in language and mathematics, with effective sizes greater for disadvantaged students than for non-disadvantaged ones. However, Kingston and Nash (2011) take issue with Black and Wiliam's research, mainly on the basis that it included studies with flawed research designs. They examined the studies that they considered eligible (13 of 300) for inclusion in a meta-analysis on formative assessment in K-12 and found a weighted mean effect size of .20. The effect

size was greater for English language arts (ELA), (.32) than for mathematics (0.17) or science (.09). Kingston and Nash attribute the stronger effect size for ELA to the fact that feedback interventions in literacy are likely to be more familiar to students, and cognitively less complex than in other domains. They also found that two types of implementation of formative assessment, one based on professional development and the other on the use of computer-based formative systems, appeared to be more effective than other approaches, such as curriculum-embedded assessments and specific use of student feedback. Ironically, Briggs et al. (2012) argue that Kingston and Nash's meta-analysis, while worthwhile, is not without error, e.g., they question the selection criteria used and pointed to potential bias in combined effect sizes.

Klute et al. (2017) found that formative assessment (in interventions of four weeks or less) had a positive effect on primary children's achievement in mathematics, reading and writing. However, whereas the source of formative assessment did not appear to be a factor in relation to achievement in mathematics, "other-directed" formative assessment (e.g., teacher or computer) had a greater impact on reading achievement than student-directed (self or peer) formative assessment. Only one study in their meta-analysis addressed student-directed formative assessment in writing. Among the limitations of the study identified by authors was the low number of studies comparing the effectiveness of different features within the student-directed and other-directed categories. In order to delve more deeply into the design features of formative assessment interventions that might influence their effectiveness and to address the changing view of the role of learners in formative assessment, Lee et al. (2020), conducted a meta-analysis of 33 US studies (K-12). They found that formative assessment had a small but significant effect on student learning. Interestingly, effects were similar for literacy, mathematics, and the arts, but lower for science. Similar to Kingston and Nash (2011), they suggest that the differences might be explained by the cognitive challenge of the tasks assessed. The different features of formative assessment interventions examined by Lee et al. include source of formative assessment feedback, formality of formative assessment evidence, cycle length of formative assessment feedback, and extent of instructional adjustments. Interventions focusing on supporting students' self-assessment as part of formative assessment had the greatest impact on achievement. They also found that other features, such as formal formative assessment evidence (e.g., written as opposed to oral feedback) and medium cycle length (1-4 weeks) had relatively strong effects. The authors conclude that, in addition to support for student-initiated self-

assessment, a dynamic interaction of features of formative assessment interventions, such as providing formal formative assessment within and between instructional units rather than within and between lessons, promoted student learning.

These findings around self-assessments corroborate those of Heitink et al. (2016) who conducted a systematic review of the prerequisites for implementation of AfL which they define as ongoing formative assessment and feedback during a lesson. They conclude that a constructivist approach to learning (described by them as a student-centred approach, with teachers and students jointly responsible for the learning process), and student autonomy in the learning and the assessment process were among the factors underpinning effective AfL in primary and post-primary contexts. The importance of involving students in the AfL process is also highlighted by Schildkamp et al. (2020).

Lane et al. (2019) examined the effects of non-digital and digital assessment on students' achievement in a range of curricular areas including reading, writing and mathematics. We draw on this review here because of its detailed focus on different curricular areas (other studies tend to look at different facets of formative assessment, such as peer-feedback or professional development, with subject-specific effects emphasised to a lesser degree). According to Lane et al., the impact of formative assessment on students' reading performance showed disappointing results. They did not find reading studies where the effects could be directly ascribed to formative assessment. However, they note that high levels of intensive and sustained professional development (PD) for teachers, addressing all aspects of formative assessment (from selecting assessment tools to translating results and evidence-based differentiated instruction) are required before formative assessment practices in reading can show robust positive effects on student performance. This will be discussed further in the section on teacher prerequisites for implementing formative assessment. The outcomes for writing were more promising. Drawing on five studies published between 2010 and 2018, Lane et al. conclude that formative assessment has a strong impact on student writing quality, particularly when cognitive strategies for planning, revising and editing, and self-regulation around writing choices are supported.

Mixed results for the effect of formative assessment on mathematics achievement were found by Lane et al. (2019). As was the case with reading, stronger studies controlled for the effect of PD. Other studies in their review reported on the effect of formative assessment (e.g., peer tutoring, computer-assisted interventions) on specific mathematics content or mathematical processes. Lane et al. are cautious in their

interpretation of these, however, as there was no moderation for factors such as PD, curriculum and instructional materials, lesson scripts, or the influence of trained experts. Notwithstanding this, in one study, formative assessment was found to have an effect on conceptual rather than procedural understanding of mathematics; in another, while there was a positive effect on overall mathematics achievement, the effect was not found for procedural understanding or for problem-solving and reasoning.

What emerges from the literature is that, while formative assessment can impact positively on attainment in literacy, mathematics and other subjects, the effects can vary greatly across studies. Bennett (2011) advises care in interpreting the effects of formative assessment, warning that “the magnitude of commonly-made quantitative claims for effectiveness is suspect, deriving from untraceable, flawed, dated, or unpublished resources” (p.5). Schildkamp et al. (2020) attribute the disappointing outcome of formative assessment in some studies to the implementation of only certain principles of formative assessment, without consideration of the broader implications for classroom practice. They argue that formative assessment needs to be an integrated element of instruction, requiring a fundamental change in the role of the teacher in the classroom, as well as a fundamental shift in power relations between teachers and students, with teachers and students becoming jointly responsible for the quality of teaching and learning in classrooms. There is evidence for the latter argument in some of the studies cited above which highlighted the central role of students in the formative assessment process. The effect of formative assessment on performance in cognitively challenging tasks is relatively weak. Both issues - the role of students and the nature of the tasks being assessed - will be examined in subsequent sections of this report.

Digital Formative Assessment

In a systematic review of the research supported by funding from the European Union, Looney (2019) examined the “state of the art” in international research and policy studies on digital formative assessment. The review sought to identify the extent to which available tools might enhance students’ learning environments, support individual student needs (via student-centred learning and assessment), and support collaborative learning and assessment. A broad range of digital tools was considered, including student e-portfolios, social media, digital textbooks, mobile learning, classroom polling, digital games and integrated formative and summative assessment. Looney defines digital

formative assessment as including:

all features of the digital learning environment that support assessment of student progress and which provide information to be used as feedback to modify the teaching and learning activities in which students are engaged. Assessment becomes 'formative' when evidence of learning is actually used by teachers and learners to adapt next steps in the learning process' (p. 10)

Looney's report is mainly descriptive in that she outlines recent advances in digital technologies specifically designed to support assessment, as well as digital tools that, although primarily designed for teaching and learning, should also provide assessment information, with the proviso that access to this information be planned in advance. However, specific evidence to support many of the technologies Looney describes (for example, effect sizes associated with successful implementation of technologies in assessing students' literacy and numeracy) is not provided in the review.

Looney notes that teachers may simply draw on digital technologies to support existing approaches to assessment, and argues instead that teachers should re-design the learning environment to support digital assessment, to provide opportunities for students' self-directed learning and assessment, and to engage learners in working collaboratively.

A systematic review by Nikou and Economides (2018) focused on the effects of using mobile devices, including Bring Your Own Devices (BYOD), on learning and motivational outcomes across a range of grade levels. Such devices can be useful in that they can provide a time- and location-independent medium for delivering personalised and context-aware learning content, and facilitate assessment and the provision of immediate feedback. Forty-three studies were reviewed, the majority of which focused on mathematics and science. Sixty percent reported positive effects on learning, 2% reported negative effects, 33% did not specify effects, and 5% were reported to be neutral (their authors did not report effect sizes). Over one-third of studies (35%) reported positive effects on student motivation, while almost three-quarters (72%) reported positive student attitudes and perceptions about mobile-based assessment. However, as the authors acknowledge, there were methodological issues associated with many of the reviewed studies, and hence care needs to be exercised at this time in drawing the conclusion that mobile devices are effective in generating formative assessment data that can be used to improve student learning.

In their critical review of the impact of technology on formative assessment and on learning outcomes in schools, See et al. (2021) drew on 55 studies. Unlike other systematic reviews, See et al. rated each of the studies in terms of its methodological rigor using a five-point scale (0 to 4) that focused on design, scale (size), attrition (dropout), outcomes, and other threats to validity. Twenty-two studies received a rating of 2 or 3 (none received a 4), and these were described in the review (overall effect sizes were not computed). See et al. identified “promising evidence” that digitally-delivered formative assessment could facilitate the learning of literacy and mathematics for young children, but effects for other subjects and for older children were weaker. However, formative assessment with technology was found to be no more effective than formative assessment without technology. The review did not find evidence for the effectiveness of learner response systems (e.g., clickers), where feedback is provided to teachers on student performance, usually on multiple-choice style items. The review also failed to identify evidence for the efficacy of technologies that embed gaming features. Given the mixed findings of their review, See et al. call for more rigorous studies using causal designs and caution against a rush to use technology on the basis of improving attainment or assessment.

Effective studies in literacy identified by See et al. include those that provided immediate feedback to teachers and students in the areas of spelling and grammar. Some software packages designed to provide individualised instruction and feedback in basic reading skills were found to be quite effective for children in the lower primary grades (compared to the upper primary grades) and for children with learning difficulties.

Aspects of online formative assessment have been found to benefit students’ performance in mathematics (Lane et al., 2019; See et al., 2021). Lane et al. (2019) report that for online formative assessment to be effective in mathematics, feedback should be given immediately and frequently. In their review it emerged that online assessment was most effective when based on specific mathematics content aligned to a clearly defined hierarchy of skills on which students could receive feedback. On the basis of a limited number of studies it appears that online formative assessment has a positive effect on student motivation - however, the authors concede that further studies are warranted to investigate any link between this and achievement in mathematics. Among the effective studies in mathematics identified by See et al. were those that used commercial diagnostic tests and online assessment tools, where automatic feedback was provided to both students and teachers. An intervention that provided adaptive

assignments to students in primary schools, based on their previous assessed performance, was found to be particularly effective in terms of improving achievement in and attitudes towards mathematics.

The use of technology as a tool in formative assessment is a relatively recent development and the findings of reviews can be limited by the quality of component studies. Two of the reviews mentioned above found that digital formative assessment enhanced student motivation. There is little evidence that formative assessment with technology is more beneficial than formative assessment without technology. Particular factors associated with the effectiveness of digital formative assessment include immediacy of feedback and the “adaptive” nature of ensuing assignments. The finding regarding the immediacy of feedback is at variance with an earlier finding by Lee et al. (2019) that medium-cycle feedback is one of the characteristics associated with positive effects in non-digital formative assessment. This inconsistency is explored further in the next section.

Nature and Quality of Feedback

As described in the introductory section, feedback is a critical component of formative assessment. It has been defined by Hattie and Timperley (2007) as “information provided by an agent (e.g., teacher, peer, book, parent, self, experience) regarding aspects of one’s performance or understanding” (p. 81), with feedback assumed to reduce the distance between current and intended learning outcomes, and confirm or modify students’ knowledge and skills. According to Wiggins (2013), effective feedback should be goal-referenced, tangible, actionable, user-friendly, timely, ongoing, consistent, and show students their progress towards a goal. Feedback can impact on domain knowledge, metacognitive knowledge, beliefs about self or tasks, and cognitive strategies (Winnie & Butler, 1994). Van der Kleij et al. (2015) note that feedback “can help students identify and correct errors and misconceptions, develop more effective and efficient problem-solving strategies, and improve self-regulation” (p. 447). According to Bangert-Drowns et al. (1991), feedback must be processed mindfully to have an impact on learning.

In a meta-analysis involving 40 studies on the provision of item-based feedback in a computer-based environment (rather than feedback based on an overall test score), Van der Kleij et al. (2015) found that elaborated feedback (defined as providing an explanation) was more effective than providing the correct answer (0.32), and much more

effective than indicating whether an answer was correct or not (0.05). Elaborated feedback was especially strong for higher-order learning outcomes. Larger effect sizes were found for mathematics, compared with social science, science and languages. Effect sizes were negatively impacted by delayed feedback. Although the results pointed in the direction of immediate feedback being more effective for lower-order learning than delayed feedback and vice versa, no significant interaction was reported. . While Van der Kleij et al. note that the effects of elaborated feedback were promising, the nature of elaborated feedback varied considerably across studies. Furthermore, there were more studies involving third-level students, compared with primary and post-primary students, in the meta-analysis, meaning that caution must be exercised in interpreting the results, and assuming that they hold across all educational levels (it was noted that primary level children, in particular, might not have the reading skills to read written-feedback, and that few of the studies employed other means of communication).

Feedback can relate to process, effort or achievement (Hattie & Timperley, 2007; Schildkamp et al., 2020). While Schildkamp et al. (2020) report on studies that found the provision of grades to students to be essential for motivation, they also note studies that found that it could negatively influence students' willingness to take risks and learn new material. They cite the value of process feedback focused on strategies to bridge the gap between where students are and where they need to be, and noted that such strategies could be explicit or implicit.

Graham et al. (2015a) conducted a meta-analysis of the available research to examine whether formative writing assessments that are directly tied to classroom teaching and learning enhance the quality of students' writing. The research focused on studies involving children in Grades 1-8 that provided feedback about quality of writing, or progress in learning specific writing skills and strategies. Across 25 studies, feedback about writing from adults (effect size = 0.87), peers (0.58), self (i.e., self-assessment) (0.62) and computers (0.38) was deemed to be effective, and it was argued that such assessments should be used more frequently by teachers. Studies that involved the provision of feedback by adults included teachers providing feedback to students on their progress in writing paragraphs, teachers giving feedback on progress on correct word sequence, spelling and total words written, (trained) parents providing feedback to their child on their writing, and verbal recorded feedback from adults on how to revise texts. The studies involving peer feedback included children giving feedback to their peers on writing quality and receiving feedback from peers (sometimes using a rubric, or a learned

strategy such as giving positive feedback followed up with feedback on aspects such as clarity or completeness). The self-assessment studies included use of a rubric to self-assess, and carrying out specific revision tactics such as substituting, adding, deleting or moving text to improve writing. The studies involving computer-based feedback were evaluations of commercially available programmes that provided students with feedback on summaries that they wrote, or on their writing more generally. Graham et al. note that, collectively, the four types of feedback were highly effective, yielding stronger effect sizes than other writing treatments such as the process writing approach, sentence combining, teaching transcription skills, using word processing and increasing how much students write.

The feedback aspect of formative assessment is important for mathematics in Early Years (EY), primary and post-primary settings, although there is some variability in the findings. In their synthesis of evidence regarding teaching of mathematics in EY and Key Stage 1, Hodgen et al. (2020) found that in each of the six studies that they identified on formative assessment and feedback, a positive effect was found. However, the effect size in each was for an intervention that included formative assessment and feedback as components among many others, and thus the evidence is regarded by the authors as limited. They also discuss “corrective” feedback which they define as “evaluating, and, if necessary, correcting children’s responses” (p.38). They found that such feedback was effective if combined with an opportunity for children to engage conceptually with the mathematics involved, through, for example, encouraging them to reflect on their problem-solving approaches, to identify solution paths or alternative solution paths, or to support their strategy selection. In their review on Key Stage 2 and 3 mathematics, Hodgen et al. (2018) conclude that findings of more general studies on the importance of feedback as part of formative assessment (such as that conducted by Kingston and Nash (2011)) apply to mathematics. They cite some (limited) evidence that feedback is particularly important for low-attaining students. They also found that feedback appears to be most effective when it is clear, task-related and encouraging of effort. Moreover, it should focus on how and why something is correct or incorrect and there should be some comparison of work with students’ previous efforts. Feedback should be used sparingly and should be delayed in the context of challenging tasks.

It is of little surprise that feedback is associated with improved performance. Grades can mitigate the positive effects of feedback and feedback based on goals is important. Elaborated feedback (defined as providing an explanation) is particularly effective,

especially for higher-order learning outcomes and conceptual learning. While feedback can focus on achievement, effort or process, process feedback aimed at strategies that bridge the gap between where students are and where they need to be, is especially effective for promoting learning. There are inconsistent findings around whether feedback should be immediate or delayed, with much depending on the nature of the task and the purpose of the feedback. The involvement of students in the feedback process is highlighted in the research. This involvement can be associated with feedback given by a teacher or other adult, or with feedback based on self- and peer-assessment. The latter is examined in more detail next.

Self- and peer-assessment

In self-assessment students make judgements about their own abilities, processes or products for the purpose of generating feedback to improve future learning and performance (Andrade, 2019). In peer-assessment students generate feedback about the performance of their peers (Double et al., 2019). While both forms of assessment can be used for summative purposes, here we report on findings related to formative assessment. In self and peer-grading (SPG) a numerical value or grade is included in the feedback. Of the 33 articles identified by Sanchez et al. (2017) as eligible for their meta-analysis on SPG in grades 3-12, the majority (20) focused on the effects of self-grading on subsequent test performance. Most of the studies were based in the US or Canada, and a range of subjects including mathematics, language arts, history, geography and science was addressed. With regard to formative assessment, both self-grading and peer-grading (SPG) benefitted subsequent achievement, although self-grading was revealed to have a larger positive effect. While this latter finding might be due to the limited number of suitable studies on peer assessment, the authors conclude that it might also relate to the effect of self-grading on metacognition and self-regulated learning, both of which are described elsewhere³ as having a significant impact on student achievement in mathematics and literacy. The positive effect of SPG on subsequent performance held for students across primary and post-primary, although no studies involved students in grades K-2 (i.e., aged less than 8 years). Almost all students were trained (e.g., through modelling, direct instruction, or practice) and used rubrics, which may have facilitated

³ See, for example, the systematic reviews on primary and post-primary numeracy completed as part of this tender.

the positive effects of SPG.

Andrade's (2019) review revealed a positive association between SA and achievement across a range of subjects. Also highlighted was a positive association between SA and self-regulated learning, substantiating Sanchez et al.'s suggestion discussed above. Her examination of studies that related to students' perceptions of SA revealed that young children had relatively unsophisticated understandings of its purpose and hence were inclined to implement it unsuccessfully. In contrast, it was found to be very useful and informative for older students (especially those in college or university). Positive perceptions were strongly linked to student agency in the process (e.g., development of own criteria), echoing findings of Lee et al. (2020) and Heitink et al. (2016), mentioned above. Andrade points to evidence that criteria used in SA should be concrete, task-specific, and graduated as in, for example, criteria for performance-based assessment.

While there were relatively few studies about peer grading in Sanchez et al.'s (2017) meta-analysis, interesting findings about peer assessment are provided by Double et al. (2019). The effect of peer assessment on subsequent performance was significant for primary, post-primary and tertiary students (although the effect size for tertiary students was lower than for the other two groupings). Peer assessment was found to be more effective than no assessment or teacher assessment and not significantly different in its effect from self-assessment. The effect did not differ between writing (majority of studies) and other subjects, and usual moderators such as use of rubrics, anonymity, or online format had no effect. While the findings on moderators, especially use of rubrics, is surprising, the authors conclude that more definitive insight into how to design effective peer assessment procedures will be generated as more studies experimentally manipulate these variables. Grading was found to be beneficial only for tertiary students. This last finding is at variance with the findings of Sanchez et al. (2017) but this may be due to the aforementioned small number of studies on peer grading in their analysis. Double et al. further suggest that grading at tertiary level is more consequential and thus students are more likely to value peer assessment that includes a grade. Another possible explanation provided by them is the difference in teaching and learning styles at tertiary level.

There are clear indications of the value of self- and peer-assessment. In one important meta-analysis, peer assessment was found to be more effective than no

assessment or teacher assessment and not significantly different in its effect from self-assessment. In another, peer-grading was not found to be beneficial for either primary or post-primary students. Both self-grading and peer-grading were found to have positive effects on subsequent achievement of students in Grades 3 - 12, although self-grading was revealed to have a larger positive effect (a finding that might relate to the limited number of studies on peer grading). Authors in the field link the particular benefits of self-assessment to metacognition and self-regulated learning, though it has been acknowledged that self-assessment can be challenging for very young children. Criteria for self-assessment should be concrete and task-specific and use of a rubric can facilitate the process.

Learning Trajectories/ Progressions

The successively more complex ways of thinking about a topic in students' learning are receiving considerable attention in research literature in mathematics and literacy. The nomenclature varies, for example, "learning paths", "learning trajectories", "learning progressions" and "progression continua", with variation both within and between how each is interpreted. They are increasingly a feature of curricula. In Ireland, for example, progression continua are included in the primary language toolkit⁴ and in the draft specification of the primary mathematics curriculum. These are intended to support teachers in formatively assessing pupils' development in the subjects concerned across their primary school years (Dunphy et al., 2014; Kennedy et al., 2012). It should be noted that the research base on the efficacy of learning trajectories/progressions as a tool for formative assessment is quite limited and is more developed for EY and early primary mathematics⁵ than for senior primary/post-primary mathematics, or for literacy.

In their PD programmes, Calkins et al. (2019) note the value of learning trajectories in supporting teachers to assess students' writing development, and provide their students with relevant feedback. The authors argue that writing rubrics often incorporate learning trajectories, and hence facilitate the sequencing of instruction and assessment by teacher. However, they found that student-facing checklists⁶ based on trajectories can be more appropriate for supporting younger students to self-assess and set goals. They also emphasise the importance of making a range of exemplars (samples of student writing

⁴ <https://curriculumonline.ie/getmedia/87033bef-fa59-41e0-87e4-4f9126e61821/Progression-Continua.pdf>

⁵ [Draft primary mathematics curriculum specification.pdf \(ncca.ie\)](#)

⁶ These checklists have been paraphrased so that they can be understood by students.

across different writing genres and different attainment levels) available to teachers *and* students to support them in interpreting learning trajectories and related tools (rubrics and checklists). For example, Deane and Sparks (2019) describe how learning progressions can be used as a basis for developing scenario-based tasks in the language arts that can provide formative assessment information relating to subskills as well as overall performance.

Hodgen et al. (2020) also point to some evidence that an understanding of developmental progressions in mathematics can support teachers in using formative assessment. They cite a study conducted by Polly et al. (2017) who used an internet-based tool that assisted educators to make diagnostic assessments in one-to-one sessions with children. Information arising from their observations of children's responses was entered into the tool, which included a built-in rubric and furnished an assessment based on the responses entered. Further teaching materials were presented based on the evidence given. The use of these formative assessment practices brought greater gains for pupils in disadvantaged school communities compared to teaching in which such an approach was not used. However, Hodgen et al (2020) also describe a study conducted by Sarama et al. (2008), in which it emerged that formative assessment premised on a learning trajectory programme, had a positive effect on children's learning if used in combination with a range of other teaching strategies such as encouraging children to share ideas, take risks and learn from and with peers in mathematics lessons. The latter point is emphasized by Dunphy et al. (2014) in the review of research on mathematics for 3-8-year olds; they argue that an understanding of general developmental progression in mathematics is one of a number of elements that are important for supporting teachers' formative assessments. There is little mention of learning trajectories in the Hodgen et al. (2018) review on Key Stage 2- 3 mathematics. This is possibly due to the fact that learning trajectories are currently most developed in the EY and early primary contexts. As mathematics curricula based on this perspective come on stream it is likely that more studies on formative assessment based on pathways/trajectories will become available.

At this time, the evidence around the use of learning trajectories to assess literacy and mathematics is incomplete, perhaps because the area is in its infancy. They seem to be helpful when incorporated into rubrics and when used in conjunction with other strategies.

Revelatory Tasks

Key to effective formative assessment are rich tasks that provide teachers with a “window into students’ thinking” (Wiliam, 2007, p.1069), on the basis of which they can form judgements about students’ cognitive processes and dispositions and decide on appropriate next steps. The use of tasks for this purpose is established in reading and, in recent years, has extended to writing (Kennedy et al., 2012). Revelatory tasks have been identified by Dooley et al. (2014) and Dooley (2019) as a key practice in formative assessment of primary mathematics. Whereas assessment in mathematics traditionally focused solely on content, emphasis is now placed on practices such as reasoning, conjecturing, using representations and tools to model real-world situations, and development of proofs as well as knowledge of concepts and procedures (Burkhardt and Schoenfeld, 2019).

In the case of literacy, tasks such as oral reading (backed up by running records and miscue analysis - see D'Agostino et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2020) and students’ recalls or summaries of what they have read have provided insights into their thinking; in recent years, think-alouds and portfolios have been used to garner insights into student thinking in writing. Traga-Philippakos and Moore (2020) recommend the use of think-aloud assessments to gain an understanding of students’ thinking processes, their use of strategies, and their attitudes towards particular tasks. They argue that such information can be used for diagnostic purposes by teachers, and to set instructional goals. They note, however, that students may benefit from training on how to engage effectively in thinking aloud. Traga-Philippakos and Moore also recommend the use of portfolios (including e-portfolios) – collections of student work gathered over time - to generate information for teachers and students about finished products and the processes used by students to arrive at those products.

Interviews with children, observation of them engaging in mathematical work, documentation of their talk and investigations of samples of work are fruitful ways for teachers to gather formative assessment information (Dooley et al., 2014; Hodgen et al., 2020). Similarly, observation by teachers of students’ engagement in complex problems and open-ended tasks shows promise as an formative assessment tool in primary and post-primary settings as these problems and tasks have potential to uncover any erroneous thinking or misconceptions learners might have (Burkhardt and Schoenfeld, 2019; McDonald & Smith, 2020). An important feature of these “revelatory” tasks is the resolution of misconceptions through structured discussion and debate with peers.

Burkhardt and Schoenfeld suggest that literature which highlights typical student misconceptions in various mathematical topics should be made available to teachers in order to focus their attention on what might unfold over the course of students' engagement with tasks of various types.

Students' mathematical thinking can be revealed in a variety of other ways. The display of collaborative problem solving on posters, and the critiquing by students of sample solutions/work are some of the strategies proposed by Burkhardt and Schoenfeld (2019). In a case study involving Grade-8 learners, Lobatao et al. (2014) found construction of diagrams to be a productive means of assessing mathematical understanding. "Writing to learn" which is defined by Graham et al. (2020) as "the use of writing as a vehicle for strengthening, extending, and deepening students' knowledge" (p.180) also offers promise as a formative assessment tool in mathematics. Concept maps - in which interlinking key concepts are depicted in a hierarchical or networked fashion - can also be used as an formative assessment tool in mathematics (Novak & Cañas, 2009). Hartmeyer et al.'s (2017) systematic review focused on the value of concept maps in science teaching and learning; however, their positive findings have implications for the use of concept mapping in mathematics. They conclude that a concept map created by an individual is useful for the revelation of personal understanding; on the other hand, a collaborative concept map allows for development of understanding and activation of learning. Concept maps that are "low directed" (i.e., in which little guidance is given) are particularly helpful for formative assessment but students who struggle with the mapping process might require some direction. The authors of one study in their review advocated teacher-constructed maps based on an individual student's knowledge as an effective means of formative assessment. Another finding of the review is that concept maps should be created during a lesson and preferably repeated on a few occasions in order to monitor students' learning. Technology-based feedback and peer assessment could be incorporated into the concept-mapping process, as it is time-consuming if implemented as recommended in the review. As described earlier, feedback should include some elaboration to support students' development as agents of their own learning.

Revelatory tasks of various types can be used for formative assessment purposes in both literacy and mathematics. The design of these tasks is challenging and demands a sophisticated understanding of subject matter on the part of teachers. In the next section we examine in more detail how teachers can be supported to develop effective formative

assessment practices. The research on formative assessment has identified a number of prerequisites that, if in place, can enhance the effects of formative assessment.

Conditions for Effective Formative Assessment

Teacher Development

According to Schildkamp et al. (2020, p. 53), “formative assessment is not an add-on activity, but rather needs to be an integrated element of instruction, which requires a fundamental change in the role of the teacher in the classroom”. Many researchers have identified teacher pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) as a prerequisite for formative assessment. PCK includes subject matter knowledge and knowledge about how to teach subject matter knowledge. Schildkamp et al. (2020) argue that teachers who lack PCK may not be able to identify student misconceptions in their subject and may not be able to give students accurate feedback on their learning and performance.

In addition to PCK, Schildkamp et al. (2000) identify assessment literacy and data literacy as key prerequisites for formative assessment. They describe assessment literacy as encompassing knowledge and skills with regard to the entire assessment process, from collecting information on student learning, to making instructional changes based on that information. Data literacy is broader; it includes assessment literacy, as well as “the collection, analysis and use of other types of data, such as student satisfaction surveys, and background information about students” (p. 5), as well as structured classroom observations. The concern is that teachers who lack this knowledge may be unable to interpret data correctly, and hence may provide inaccurate feedback to students and/or parents. They may determine incorrect actions to take in the classroom, in such areas as reteaching certain content, grouping students, or differentiating instruction. Schildkamp et al. (2020) conducted a meta-analysis based on 54 studies and identified the following key factors that should be taken into account in planning teacher professional development for formative assessment:

- *Knowledge and skill* - data literacy was identified as a key aspect of teacher knowledge for formative assessment. It includes assessment literacy as well as the collection, analysis, and use of other types of data, such as student satisfaction surveys, and background information about students. Other key aspects were PCK, goal setting, feedback (content, timing, type), facilitating classroom discussions, and ICT skills (information management systems, assessment systems).

- *Social factors* - these include collaboration among teachers in discussing assessment data, and involvement of students in the assessment process, through peer and self-assessment.
- *Psychological factors* - these pertain to positive attitudes/beliefs, ownership over assessment results and student learning, and perceived control. Schildkamp et al. use the term “social pressure” to describe the pressure on teachers to improve student performance based on formative assessment. This can be positive when it constitutes support and encouragement from school leaders; however, it can also include pressure to raise performance, which can be counterproductive as it can detract from teacher autonomy.

In relation to teacher development, Looney (2019) identifies the following as important:

- integrating effective formative assessment into lesson plans;
- responding effectively to evidence of student learning and needs;
- providing opportunities for students to direct their own learning; and
- understanding the potentials and limits of different digital tools.

Regarding literacy, Lane et al. (2019) note a requirement for high levels of intensive and sustained PD for teachers, addressing all aspects of formative assessment (from selecting assessment tools to translating results and evidence-based differentiated instruction) before formative assessment practices in reading can show robust positive effects on student performance.

PD also seems to be at the core of effective formative assessment in mathematics. However, Lane et al. (2019) conclude – on the basis of two high-quality studies – that while PD can have an impact on teachers’ understanding of formative assessment in the classroom, it has little effect on students’ mathematics achievement. The difficulty that teachers experience when putting their pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) into practice and making in-the-moment decisions to enhance students’ mathematics learning is highlighted in the studies concerned. In another study in Lane et al.’s review where similar results were found, it was argued that PD should extend over a considerable period of time and involve expert support in order to benefit teachers’ practices in formative assessment. Burkhardt and Schoenfeld (2019) also maintain that effective formative assessment practices are contingent on teachers’ PCK which takes time to evolve. However they make the point that implementing formative assessment is also “a

matter of inclination” (p.43). The tradition of assessing students’ understanding through weekly and termly short-item tests - which is more ingrained in mathematics than in literacy- is a particular challenge that needs to be overcome.

Yan et al. (2021), who conducted a systematic review of teachers’ intentions and practices regarding formative assessments, report that a range of teacher factors such as instrumental attitude (perceived usefulness), self-efficacy, and professional development need attention. They also note that contextual factors including internal school support, and access to dedicated time and resources are important. These latter school-level aspects are examined in greater detail in the next subsection.

Lysaght and O’Leary (2013, 2017) specifically addressed the implementation of assessment for learning (formative assessment) in Irish primary schools. In general, teachers in a sample of primary schools in Ireland achieved low average scores on the Assessment for Learning Audit Instrument (AfLAI), a tool designed to identify levels of formative assessment in four subareas: sharing learning intentions and success criteria, questioning and classroom discussion, feedback, and peer- and self-assessment, with lowest scores on peer- and self-assessment (Lysaght & O’Leary, 2013). In a follow-up study, Lysaght and O’Leary (2017) demonstrated how a collaborative, school-level approach to professional development that involved the use of the AfLAI could be effective in beginning to address gaps in teachers’ understanding and implementation of assessment for learning. .

Support at School Level

In addition to ensuring that teachers have access to relevant professional development, where they can reflect on their use of formative assessment, and the effects of feedback on students’ learning, schools and school leaders can provide additional supports to promote the implementation of formative assessments. Noting that strong school leadership is associated with higher fidelity implementation of formative assessment strategies by teachers following professional development, Lane et al. (2019)⁷ argue that support structures at school level should include:

- School leaders who understand formative assessment, and can provide a rationale for its use, as well as a supportive and non-threatening environment, where

⁷ Lane et al.’s review of this aspect of formative assessment was based on a review of the available literature, rather than a meta-analysis or other form of systematic review.

effective use of assessment data is modelled for teachers;

- A commitment to providing teachers with regular and protected meeting time for meaningful examination of assessment practices and preparation of assessments, feedback and instructional responses;
- Provision of professional learning that is sustained, collaborative, work-embedded and situated within school needs;
- Leaders who can align expertise and resources to support teachers' learning about how to use assessment results, and deploy resources to cover a range of data-related functions (e.g., within-school support for clerical aspects of formative assessment);
- Development of communities of practice focused on improving formative assessment practice;
- Decentralised organisational structures at school level, and distributed leadership, so accountability pressure on teachers do not lead to unintended impacts on instructional and assessment practices.

Lane et al. also note factors that might prevent effective implementation of formative assessment, including a school culture focused on high-stakes summative examinations, a focus on curriculum coverage rather than on the achievement of learning outcomes, and lack of teacher collaboration. The corollary of this is that formative assessment is easier to implement in systems in which formative and summative assessment are integrated to the greatest extent possible.

The focus of an evidence review by Newman et al. (2021) and subsequent best practice guidance report (Education Endowment Foundation (EEF), 2021) is on the provision of effective feedback to students (an element of effective formative assessment practice). The EEF recommends the development and implementation of a school-level feedback policy that prioritises and exemplifies the principles of effective feedback, with attention to the following:

- Examination of costs associated with feedback practices, including opportunity costs associated with written feedback; promotion of time-efficient methods to mitigate teacher workload, as long as they are not detrimental to pupils' learning;
- Support for teacher autonomy to exercise their evidence-informed professional judgement alongside provision of worked examples of effective feedback practices;

- A focus on broad policy rather than on surface features of feedback (a specific frequency, the colour of the pen used for written feedback, or the use of ‘verbal feedback stamps’ which provide a record of verbal feedback, but have no real purpose associated with improving learning);
- Emphasis on enhancing students’ learning, rather than making judgements about a teacher’s performance or meeting parents’ expectations (for example, the nature and frequency of written vs. verbal feedback);
- Communication of changes in feedback policy and/or practices (for example, a change in the balance between written or visible feedback and verbal feedback) to students and parents;
- Linking of feedback policy to different aspects of effective instruction (e.g., clear communication of learning outcomes, gathering of valid assessment evidence).

Discussion

The review we conducted was guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent does formative assessment, including digital formative assessment, improve students’ performance in literacy and numeracy?
2. What factors are associated with effective formative assessment in literacy and numeracy?
3. What supports can facilitate the successful implementation of formative assessment in classrooms and schools?

To what extent does formative assessment, including digital formative assessment, improve students’ performance in literacy and numeracy?

Early studies reported strong effects of formative assessment on student performance (as measured by standardised tests). For example, Black and Wiliam (1998a) reported effect sizes between .40 and .70, suggesting that formative assessment could have very powerful effects. More recent meta-analyses, which have imposed stricter criteria on the selection of studies, have reported more modest effects, with, for example, Kingston and Nash (2011) reporting a weighted mean of .20, and larger effect sizes for English language arts than for mathematics. Lee et al. (2020) also reported modest effect sizes for formative assessment, with an average (d) of .29, and larger effects for literacy and mathematics, compared with science.

As might be expected, more recent meta-analyses have examined the effects of formative assessment on performance when various digital tools have been used. In

general, the results have been disappointing, though mainly because the underlying studies have not been well-designed or implemented. Hence, although Nikou and Economides (2018) found positive effects for the use of mobile devices on learning in 60% of the studies they reviewed, and positive effects on motivation in 35% of the studies, they advised caution in interpreting these findings because of the poor underlying quality of the studies. See et al. (2021) identify “promising evidence” that digitally-delivered formative assessment can facilitate the learning of aspects of literacy (basic reading skills, aspects of spelling and grammar) and mathematics (number operations) for young children and those with learning difficulties. However, formative assessment with technology was found by them to be no more effective than formative assessment without technology, and studies could not confirm the effectiveness of electronic learner response systems (e.g., clickers) or technologies that embed gaming features.

Despite the absence of robust effect sizes associated with the implementation of formative assessment in recent meta-analyses and systematic reviews, the research is more nuanced than earlier studies in that efforts are often made to identify factors associated with positive effect sizes. These mitigating factors cover a number of areas, including the frequency and type of feedback offered (whether by teachers or electronically), the involvement of students in generating formative assessment (for example, self-assessment), and the extent to which teachers are prepared to implement formative assessment, and follow through on addressing students’ assessed needs. These are considered under the next question.

What factors are associated with effective formative assessment in literacy and numeracy?

The main factors associated with effective formative assessment that emerged from this review of the literature are as follows: source of feedback (including self- and peer-assessment); quality of feedback; learning trajectories/pathways; revelatory tasks; pedagogical content knowledge; and professional development.

Source of feedback

Feedback is a critical component of formative assessment. It can emanate from an adult, self, peer or through technology. As reported by Graham et al. (2015), all forms of feedback are effective but self-assessment and, to a slightly lesser extent, peer-assessment have a significant impact on learning. However, very young children can

struggle with the process as they might not understand its purpose. In general the assignment of a grade by a peer is not recommended for primary or post-primary students. On the other hand, self-grading is found to be effective probably because it promotes metacognition and self-regulation on the part of the student. There are mixed findings regarding the role of rubrics in peer and self-assessment possibly due to the limited number of studies in the area.

Quality of feedback

Feedback appears to be most effective when it is clear, task-related and encouraging of student effort. It can focus on achievement, effort or process. There is evidence that process feedback with a focus on strategies to bridge the gap between where students are and where they need to be is particularly valuable. Aligned with this, elaborated feedback which is described as defined as providing an explanation has been found to be more effective than providing the correct answer and considerably more effective than indicating whether an answer is correct or not. Some care must be taken in how feedback is given to young children who might have difficulty making sense of written comments. Findings regarding timing of feedback are varied. The immediacy of feedback, especially on digital devices, emerges as beneficial to student learning. However, it has also been found that feedback should be delayed in the case of challenging or higher-order tasks. Much depends on the context: sometimes a student might need immediate feedback in order to progress in a task (e.g., where the student is uncertain how to proceed); at other times immediate feedback might detract from students' "productive struggle" that is conducive to their engagement with cognitively challenging tasks (Burkhardt & Schoenfeld, 2019).

Learning trajectories/pathways

There is some evidence that learning trajectories/pathways can facilitate formative assessment, However, findings are limited and are mainly found in the field of early mathematics due to the seminal work of Clements and Sarama (2009). Combined with other approaches to teaching and learning, teachers' use of learning trajectories as a formative assessment tool can impact positively on students' mathematical development. In the area of literacy – specifically writing – it has been suggested that student-facing checklists that are based on trajectories can support students to self-assess and set goals, a

suggestion that could be applied to other curricular areas. Samples of student writing across different writing genres and different attainment levels could be made available to teachers and students to assist them in interpreting learning trajectories. The use of learning trajectories as part of the design of technological assessment holds some promise as this allows for adaptive feedback. There is reference to learning trajectories/pathways in primary mathematics and literacy curriculum documentation in Ireland which has potential to support formative assessment in literacy and numeracy. However, as mentioned above the research base is strongest at early primary levels. Further research is required to develop learning pathways in maths and literacy that are relevant for senior primary and post-primary learners.

Revelatory tasks

Formative assessment is an integral component of pedagogy, entailing a focus by teachers on how different learners in their classroom construct knowledge. It demands that teachers carefully attend to how students are thinking and reasoning. Revelatory tasks have potential in this regard as they allow teachers to garner insight into students' knowledge and misconceptions and also their disposition to the subject(s) involved and their motivation to engage. Rich tasks where students experience some cognitive challenge are particularly important in this regard but all pedagogical tasks – from routine to non-routine – should facilitate ongoing formative assessment. Teachers should gather data as appropriate from students' engagement in these tasks as evidentiary warrants, for example, e-portfolios, work samples, documentation of talk, diagrams, mathematical solution processes and so on. Some of this data is subject specific, for example running records in literacy, problem-solving in mathematics. The data can also emanate from other curricular subjects, such as an integrated project that might make demands of a student's literacy and/or numeracy skills.

Teacher Knowledge/Inclination

Formative assessment is demanding of teachers because they have to act “in the moment” as students reveal their thinking in classroom interactions or over the course of engaging with a task. They have to decide whether immediate feedback is required and, if so, the nature of that feedback. Coupled with this, teachers require a knowledge of students' misconceptions in different curricular areas and the pedagogical strategies that might help to address these misconceptions. They need an understanding

of learning trajectories/pathways in order to design appropriate learning tasks for their students as well as to assess individuals' learning and the support or extension they might be warranted. This entails the development of PCK relevant to literacy and numeracy as well as an understanding and knowledge of formal and informal assessment processes. It also requires that teachers be prepared to relinquish control to students as they set goals for learning together, and decide on how these goals might be reached. Facilitation of self- and peer-assessment demands a change in mindset from one where the teacher takes full responsibility for assessment to one where students are given autonomy in the process with supports made available to learners as appropriate.

What supports can facilitate the successful implementation of formative assessment in classrooms and schools?

The research literature identifies a number of factors that should be in place at school level to support effective formative assessment and the provision of effective feedback to students. Some of these relate to professional development, while others focus on the role of the teacher in deciding on the nature and frequency of feedback.

Where professional development is concerned, the research indicates that school leaders should provide teachers with regular and protected meeting time for meaningful examination of assessment practice and preparation of assessments, feedback and instructional response. Moreover, it is recognised that professional learning should be sustained, collaborative, work-embedded and situated within school needs.

Unsurprisingly, the literature suggests that school leaders should understand formative assessment, be able to provide a rationale for its use, and provide a non-threatening environment where effective use of assessment data is modelled for teachers. Decentralised organisational structures at school level, and distributed leadership are recommended, to ensure that accountability pressure on teachers does not lead to unintended impacts on instructional and assessment processes.

Research on the development of feedback policy at school level indicates that policies should offer suggestions on making feedback more manageable, and provide detailed examples, but that specific methods and features should be decided by teachers themselves, thereby supporting teacher autonomy to exercise their evidence-informed professional judgement. Moreover, it is acknowledged that effective feedback is linked to other aspects of teaching and learning, such as effective instructional methods and access to an appropriate range of assessment tools.

References⁸

- *Andrade, H.L. (2019). A critical review of research on student self-assessment. *Frontiers in Education*, 4, Article 87. 10.3389/educ.2019.00087
- Atherton, C. (2018). *Assessment. Evidence-based teaching for enquiring teachers*. Critical Publishing.
- *Bennett, R. (2011). Formative assessment: A critical review. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*. 18. 10.1080/0969594X.2010.513678.
- Bangert-Drowns, R. L., Kulik, C. C., Kulik, J. A., & Morgan, M. T. (1991). The instructional effect of feedback in test-like events. *Review of Educational Research*, 61, 213–238. doi:10.3102/00346543061002213
- Black, P., & Wiliam, D. (1998a). Assessment and classroom learning, *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 5 (1), 7-74. 10.1080/0969595980050102
- Black, P, & Wiliam, D. (1998b), Inside the black box: Raising standards through classroom assessment. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 80 (2), 139-148.
- Bloom, B. S. (1969). Some theoretical issues relating to educational evaluation. In R. W. Tyler (Ed.), *Educational evaluation: new roles, new means: the 63rd yearbook of the National Society for the Study of Education (part II)* (Vol. 69(2), pp. 26-50). University of Chicago Press.
- *Briggs, D. C., Ruiz-Primo, M. A., Furtak, E., Shepard, L., & Yin, Y. (2012). Meta-analytic methodology and inferences about the efficacy of formative assessment. *Educational Measurement: Issues & Practice*, 31(4), 13–17. Education Research Complete.
- Burkhardt, H., & Schoenfeld, A. H. (2019). Formative assessment in mathematics. In R. Bennett, G. Cizek, & H. Andrade (Eds.), *Handbook of formative assessment in the disciplines* (pp. 35-67). New York: Routledge.
- *Calkins, L. Ehrenworth, M., & Akhmedjanova, D. (2019). Creating formative assessment systems in the teaching of writing, and harnessing them as professional development. In H. Andrade, R. E. Bennett & G. Cizek (Eds.), *Handbook of formative assessment in the disciplines* (pp., 173-206). Routledge.
- Cizek, G. J., Andrade, H. L., and Bennett, R. E. (2019). Formative assessment: history, definition, and progress. In H. L. Andrade, R. E. Bennett, and G. J. Cizek (Eds.), *Handbook of formative assessment in the disciplines* (pp. 3-19). Routledge.
- Clements, D., & Sarama, J. (2009). *Learning and teaching early math: The learning*

⁸ Systematic reviews and meta-analyses that informed this report are indicated with an asterisk.

trajectories approach. UK: Routledge.

- D'Agostino, J.V., Rodgers, E., Winkler, C., Johnson, T., & Berenbon, R. (2021) The generalizability of running record accuracy and self-correction scores. *Reading Psychology, 42*(2), 111-130. DOI: [10.1080/02702711.2021.1880177](https://doi.org/10.1080/02702711.2021.1880177)
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly, 13*(3), 319–340.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2002). *Handbook of self-determination research*. Rochester, NY: University of Rochester Press
- Deane, P., & Sparks, J.R. (2019). Scenario-based formative assessment of key practices in the language arts. In H. Andrade, R. E. Bennett & G. Cizek (Eds.), *Handbook of formative assessment in the disciplines* (pp., 68-96). Routledge.
- Dooley, T., Dunphy, E. & Shiel, G., with D. Butler, D. Corcoran, T. Farrell, S.Nic Mhuirí, M. O'Connor and J. Travers. (2014). Mathematics in early childhood and primary education (children aged 3-8 years). Research Report No.18: Teaching and learning. Retrieved from https://www.ncca.ie/media/2147/ncca_research_report_18.pdf
- Dooley, T. (2019). Learning and teaching primary mathematics: An addendum to NCCA research reports 17 and 18. NCCA. Accessed at: https://ncca.ie/media/4087/primary_maths_research_addendum_2019.pdf
- *Double, K.S., McGrane, J.A. & Hopfenbeck, T.N. (2020). The impact of peer assessment on academic performance: A meta-analysis of control group studies. *Educational Psychology Review, 32*, 481–509 [10.1007/s10648-019-09510-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-019-09510-3)
- Dunphy, E., Dooley, T., & Shiel, G., with D. Butler, D. Corcoran, M. Ryan, and J. Travers. (2014). *Mathematics in early childhood and primary education (children aged 3-8 years)*. Research Report No.17: Definitions, theories, stages of development and progression. Retrieved from http://www.ncca.ie/en/Publications/Reports/NCCA_Research_Report_17.pdf
- Education Endowment Foundation. (2021). *Teacher feedback to improve pupil learning. Guidance report*. Author. Accessed at: <https://educationendowmentfoundation.org.uk/education-evidence/guidance-reports/feedback>
- Gallagher, H.A., Arshan, N. and Woodworth, K. (2017). Impact of the National Writing Project's college-ready writers program in high-need rural districts. *Journal of*

Research on Educational Effectiveness, 10(3), 570-595.

- *Graham, S., Hebert, M., & Harris, K. (2015). Formative assessment and writing: A meta-analysis. *Elementary School Journal*, 115(4), 523-547.
<https://doi.org/10.1086/681947>
- Graham S., Kiuahara, S.A., & MacKay, M. (2020). The effects of writing on learning in science, social studies, and mathematics: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 90(2), 179-226. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654320914744>
- *Hartmeyer, R., Stevenson, M., & Bentsen, P. (2017). A systematic review of concept mapping-based formative assessment processes in primary and secondary science education. *Assessment in Education, Principles, Policy & Practice*, 25(6), 598-619.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594X.2017.1377685>
- Hattie, J., & Timperley, H. (2007). The power of feedback. *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 81-112. <https://doi.org/10.3102/003465430298487>
- *Heitink, M. C., van der Kleij, F., Veldkamp, B. P., Schildkamp, K., & Kippers, W. B. (2016). A systematic review of prerequisites for implementing assessment for learning in classroom practice. *Educational Research Review*, 17, 50-62.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2015.12.002>
- *Hodgen, J., Foster, C., Marks, R., & Brown, M. (2018). *Evidence for review of mathematics teaching: Improving mathematics in Key Stages Two and Three: Evidence review*. London: Education Endowment Foundation. Accessed at: [EEF Maths Evidence Review.pdf \(d2tic4wvo1iusb.cloudfront.net\)](https://www.educationendowmentfoundation.org.uk/public/files/EEF_Maths_Evidence_Review.pdf)
- *Hodgen, J., Barclay, N., Foster, C., Gilmore, C., Marks, R. and Simms, V. (2020). *Early years and Key Stage 1 mathematics teaching: Evidence review*. London: Education Endowment Foundation. Accessed at: https://educationendowmentfoundation.org.uk/public/files/Early_Years_and_Key_Stage_1_Mathematics_Evidence_Review.pdf
- MacArthur, C.A. (2016). Instruction in evaluation and revision. In C. A. MacArthur, S. Graham, & J.Fitzgerald (Eds.), *Handbook of writing research* (pp. 272-287). New York: Guilford.
- McDonald, P. & Smith, J. (2019). Improving mathematical learning in Scotland's Curriculum for Excellence through problem posing: an integrative review. *The Curriculum Journal*, 31 (3), 398-4365. <https://doi.org/10.1002/curj.15>
- Kennedy, E., Dunphy L., Dwyer, B., Hayes, G., McPhillips, T., Marsh, J., O'Connor, M., & Shiel, G. (2012). *Literacy in early childhood and primary education (3-8 years)*.

NCCA Research Report, no. 15. Dublin: NCCA.

- *Kingston, N., & Nash, B. (2011). Formative assessment: A meta-analysis and call for research. *Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice*, 30(4), 28-37.
- *Klute, M., Apthorp, H., Harlacher, J., & Reale, M. (2017). *Formative assessment and elementary school student academic achievement: A review of the evidence* (REL 2017–259). U.S. Department of Education, Institute of Education Sciences, National Center for Education Evaluation and Regional Assistance, Regional Educational Laboratory Central.
- *Lane, R, Parrila, R, Bower, M, Bull, R, Cavanagh, M, Forbes, A, Jones, T, Leaper, D, Khosronejad, M, Pellicano, L, Powell, S, Ryan, M, & Skrebneva, I. (2019). *Formative assessment evidence and practice literature review*. Australian Curriculum and Assessment Reporting Authority, Educator Services Australia, and the Australian Institute for Teaching and School Leadership.
- *Lee, H., Chung, H.Q., Zhang, Y., Abedi, J., & Warschauer, M. (2020). The effectiveness and features of formative assessment in US K-12 education: A systematic review. *Applied Measurement in Education*, 33(2), 124-140, DOI: [10.1080/08957347.2020.1732383](https://doi.org/10.1080/08957347.2020.1732383)
- Lobato, J., Hohensee, C. & Diamond, J. (2013). What can we learn by comparing students' diagram-construction processes with the mathematical conceptions inferred from their explanations with completed diagrams?. *Mathematics Education Research Journal*, 26, 607-634. 10.1007/s13394-013-0106-3.
- *Looney, A. (2019). *Digital formative assessment: A review of the literature*. assess@learning Accessed at: <http://www.eun.org/documents/411753/817341/Assess%40Learning+Literature+Review/be02d527-8c2f-45e3-9f75-2c5cd596261d>
- Lysaght, Z., & O'Leary, M. (2013). An instrument to audit teachers' use of assessment for learning. *Irish Educational Studies*, DOI:10.1080/03323315.2013.784636
- Lysaght, Z., & O'Leary, M. (2017). Scaling up, writ small: using an assessment for learning audit instrument to stimulate site-based professional development, one school at a time. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 24(2), 271-289. DOI:10.1080/0969594X.2017.1296813
- *Newman, M., Kwan, I., Shucan Bird, K., Hoo, H.T. (2021). *The impact of feedback on student attainment: A systematic review*. Education Endowment Foundation. Accessed at: <https://d2tic4wvo1iusb.cloudfront.net/documents/guidance/Systematic->

[Review-of-Feedback-EPPI-2021.pdf](#)

- *Nikou, S.A., & Economedes, A.A. (2018). Mobile-based assessment: A literature review of publications in major refereed journals from 2009 to 2018. *Computers & Education, 125*, 101-119.
- Novak, J. D., & Cañas, A. J. (2009). The development and evolution of the concept mapping tool leading to a new model for mathematics education. In K. Afamasaga-Fuata'i (Ed.), *Concept mapping in mathematics: Research into practice* (pp. 3-16). Boston, MA: Springer
- OECD. (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development). (2005, November). *Policy brief: Formative Assessment: Improving learning in secondary classrooms*. Paris: Author.
- Philippakos, Z. A., & McAurther, C.A. (2016). The effects of giving feedback on the persuasive writing of fourth- and fifth-grade students. *Reading Research Quarterly, 51*(4). Doi:101002/rrq.149
- *Sanchez, C. E., Atkinson, K. M., Koenka, A. C., Moshontz, H., & Cooper, H. (2017). Self-grading and peer-grading for formative and summative assessments in 3rd through 12th grade classrooms: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 109*(8), 1049–1066. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000190>
- Sarama, J., Clements, D. H., Starkey, P., Klein, A., & Wakeley, A. (2008). Scaling up the implementation of a pre-kindergarten mathematics curriculum: Teaching for understanding with trajectories and technologies. *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness, 1*(2), 89-119.
- Scriven, M. (1967). The methodology of evaluation. In R.W. Tyler, R.M. Gagne, and M. Scriven (Eds.). In *Perspectives of curriculum evaluation* (39-83). Chicago, IL: Rand McNally.
- *Schildkamp, K., van der Kleij, F.M., Heitink, M.C., Kippers, W.B., & Veldkamp, B.P. (2020). Formative assessment: A systematic review of critical teacher prerequisites for classroom practice. *International Journal of Educational Research, 50-62*, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2015.12.002>
- *See, B. H., Gorard, S., Lu, B., Dong, L., & Siddiqui, N. (2021). Is technology always helpful?: A critical review of the impact on learning outcomes of education technology in supporting formative assessment in schools, *Research Papers in Education*, DOI: 10.1080/02671522.2021.1907778
- Sparks, S. D. (2015). Types of assessments: A head-to-head comparison. *Education*

Week, 35(12), p. S2.

Tzci, E., & Dikici., A. (2006). The effects of digital portfolio assessment process on students' writing and drawing performance. *Turkish Online Journal of Technology*, 5(2). Accessed at: <http://www.tojet.net/articles/v5i2/527.pdf>

Traga Philippakos, Z. A. & Moore, N. S. (2020). Formative assessment on writing: Affordances and challenges in elementary settings. In C. Martin, D. Polly and R. Lambert (Eds.), *Handbook of research on formative assessment in Pre-K through elementary classrooms* (pp. 282-306). Hershey, PA: IGI Global.

*Van der Kleij, F.M., Feskens, R.C.W., & Eggen, T.H.M. (2015). Effects of feedback in a computer-based learning environment on students' learning outcomes: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 85(4), 475-511.

Wang, Y., Compton-Lilly, C., & Sanchez, L. (2020). Formative reading assessments of running records and miscue analysis: Limits and possibilities for literacy learning. In C. Martin, D. Polly and R. Lambert (Eds.), *Handbook of research on formative assessment in Pre-K through elementary classrooms* (pp. 327-345). Hershey, PA: IGI Global.

Wiggins, G. (2012). Seven keys to effective feedback. *Educational Leadership*, 70(1), 10–16.

Wiliam, Dylan. (2006). Formative assessment: Getting the focus right. *Educational Assessment*, 11, 283-289. 10.1207/s15326977ea1103&4_7.

Wiliam, D. (2007). Keeping learning on track: Classroom assessment and the regulation of learning. In F. K. Lester Jr. (Ed.), *Second handbook of mathematics teaching and learning* (pp. 1053-1098). Greenwich, CT: Information Age Publishing.

Wiliam D. (2016). *Leadership for teacher learning: Creating a culture where all students improve so that all students succeed*. Learning Sciences International.

Winne, P. H., & Butler, D. L. (1994). Student cognition in learning from teaching. In T. Husen & T. Postlewaite (Eds.), *International encyclopaedia of education* (2nd ed., pp. 5738–5745). Oxford, England: Pergamon.

*Yan, Z., Li, Z., Panadero, E., Yang, M., Yang, L. & Lao, H. (2021). A systematic review on factors influencing teachers' intentions and implementations regarding formative assessment. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 28(3), 228-260.

Author Biographies

Dr Gerry Shiel is former Research Fellow at Educational Research Centre, Dublin. He has overseen several large-scale assessments, including the OECD Programme for International Student Assessment and National Assessments of Reading Literacy and Mathematics. He has also been involved in the development of standardised tests and has been author or co-author of a number of commissioned studies in the areas of English language, mathematics and assessment on behalf of the National Council for Curriculum and Assessment. These studies have involved extensive literature reviews.

Dr Thérèse Dooley is Emeritus Associate Professor of Mathematics Education at DCU Institute of Education. One of the lead authors of the NCCA desktop review of research on mathematics education at early-childhood level, she authored an addendum on middle/upper primary mathematics. She was a member of the STEM Education Review Group that conducted a comprehensive review of STEM Education in Irish schools, and was Chair of the Tenth Conference of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education held in Dublin in 2017. Passionate about learners' development of powerful mathematical thinking, she continues to work, research and publish in the area.

Appendix 1:

Research Questions

1. To what extent does formative assessment, including digital formative assessment, improve students' performance in literacy and numeracy?
2. What factors are associated with effective formative assessment in literacy and numeracy?
3. What supports can facilitate the successful implementation of formative assessment in classrooms and schools?

Key Data Sources Consulted

The following databases were searched:

- (a) EBSCO Education Research Complete
- (b) EBSCO ERIC
- (c) Scopus.
- (d) Google Scholar

Search Terms

Sample search string (Educational Research Complete/Ebscohost)

(formative assessment) AND ((maths education or numeracy or math* literacy or math* or STEM) OR (literacy or reading or reading skills or literacy skills)) AND (meta-analysis or systematic review or literature review or meta analysis or overview or review or meta-synthesis or meta synthesis)

Sample search string (Scopus)

S1 DE "STEM education"; S2 STEM Education; S3 S1 OR S2; S4 DE "MATHEMATICS education"; S5 math* education; S6 S4 OR S5; S7 S3 OR S6; S8 math* teaching or numeracy or math* literacy or math*; S9 S7 OR S8; S10 meta-analysis or systematic review and S9; S10 (secondary education or high school or junior high or middle school or secondary school or k6-12 or ks3 or post primary or ks4) AND S9; S11 S10 NOT (higher education or tertiary education); S12 (meta-analysis or systematic review) AND S11

Grey literature

‘Grey’ literature was identified through hand searches, for example, Hodgen et al. (2018) and Baker et al. (2015). Reviews found in the grey literature that draw on a substantial number of studies are included in our tabulation.

Summary of Papers Reviewed

Upon screening of abstracts and full texts, 22 studies were selected for inclusion in this review (Figure 1). A summary of these studies, and their key findings, is presented in Table 1.

Figure 1: Prisma Chart Summarising Outcomes of Searches

Table 1: Tabulation of Included Studies

Review (Authors)	Number of studies	Overall effect size	Focus [Age Range]	Key Findings
Andrade, H.L. (2019). A critical review of research on student self-assessment. <i>Frontiers in Education</i> , 4, Article 87.	76	n/a	Student self-assessment. [Grade 1 to graduate level, and several included pre-service teachers]	Four most common topic categories of studies on self-assessment (SA): consistency, achievement, student perceptions, and self-regulated learning (SRL). Summative SA tends to be inconsistent with external judgements but can be improved by factors such as experience, use of feedback and rubrics. Limited evidence on relationship between accuracy in formative SA, and students' subsequent study behaviors. Some evidence that correlation between after-task self-assessment and task performance is higher than for generic self-assessment. Formative forms of self-assessment found to have a positive effect on student achievement. Students positively disposed towards formative SA, particularly if they have agency in process, e.g., development of own rubrics; older children have more sophisticated understanding of purposes of SA. Positive association between SA and SRL.
Bennett, R.(2011). Formative assessment: A critical review. <i>Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice</i> . 18. (1), 5-25.	n/a	n/a	Examines six interrelated topics, denoted as follows: the definitional issue, the effectiveness issue, the domain dependency issue, the measurement issue, the professional development issue, and the system issue. [Primary/ secondary]	Literature review examining the definition of formative assessment, the claims commonly made for its effectiveness, the limited attention given to domain considerations in its conceptualisation, the under-representation of measurement principles in that conceptualisation, the teacher-support demands formative assessment entails, and the impact of the larger educational system. Concludes that the term, 'formative assessment' does not yet represent a well-defined set of artefacts or practices. The magnitude of commonly made quantitative claims for effectiveness is viewed as suspect, deriving from untraceable, flawed, dated, or unpublished sources. For greatest benefit, formative approaches should be conceptualised as part of a comprehensive assessment system in which all components work together to facilitate learning.
Briggs, D., Ruiz-Primo, M., Furtak, E., Shepard, L., Yin, Y. (2012). Meta-Analytic methodology and inferences about the efficacy of formative	n/a	n/a	Efficacy of formative assessment. [K-12]	Critique of Kingston and Nash (2011); Focuses on four methodological concerns about the Kingston and Nash meta-analysis: (1) approach taken to select studies for inclusion, (2) application of study inclusion criteria, (3) extent to which the effect sizes being combined are biased, and (4) relationship between effect size magnitude and characteristics of outcome measures. After examining these issues in the context of the Kingston and Nash review, it is

assessment. <i>Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice</i> , 31(4), 13-17.				concluded that considerable uncertainty remains about the effect that formative assessment practices has on student achievement.
Calkins, L. Ehrenworth, M., & Akhmedjanova, D. (2019). Creating formative assessment systems in the teaching of writing, and harnessing them as professional development. In H. Andrade, R. E. Bennett & G. Cizek (Eds.), <i>Handbook of formative assessment in the disciplines</i> (pp., 173-206). Routledge.	n/a	n/a	Approach to formative assessment of writing [K-12]	Descriptive study giving detailed information on the authors' Writing Pathways project, which provides schools and teachers with a range of supports for implementing formative assessment. Outlines how trajectories of writing development (as evidenced in checklists, rubrics and benchmark exemplars) can be used to support students' writing development. Examines how student-facing checklists, combined with student exemplars, can help students become more independent and expert at formative assessment and goal-setting. Some reference is made to the requirements of the Common Core Standards as they relate to the teaching and assessment of writing.
Double, K.S., McGrane, J.A. & Hopfenbeck, T.N. (2020). The impact of peer assessment on academic performance: A meta-analysis of control group studies. <i>Educational Psychology Review</i> , 32, 481–509.	55	0.31	Effect of peer assessment interventions on academic performance [Primary, secondary, tertiary]	Results suggest that peer assessment improves academic performance compared with no assessment (0.31) and with teacher assessment (0.28), but is not significantly different in its effect from self-assessment (0.23). Effect of peer assessment similar across primary, post-primary and tertiary; effect did not differ between writing (the majority of studies) and other subjects; effect same if assessment contained written component; grading (in the context of self-assessment) beneficial for tertiary students only; factors such as freeform, anonymity and online (vs. not online) had no effect.
Graham, S., Hebert, M., & Harris, K. (2015). Formative assessment and writing: A meta-analysis. <i>Elementary School</i>	27	0.61	Impact of adult, peer, self, and computer feedback on quality of student writing. [Grades 1-8]	Feedback to students about writing from adults, peers, self, and computers statistically enhanced writing quality yielded an average effect size of 0.27, with effect sizes varying according to the source of feedback – adults (0.87), peers (0.58), self (0.62) and computer (0.38), though the numbers of studies in each of these categories was small (e.g., 4 studies for computer-based feedback). Neither teachers' monitoring of

<i>Journal</i> , 115(4), 523-547.				students' writing progress (based on five studies using pre-packaged programmes) or implementation of the 6 + 1 Trait Writing model (based on 4) was found to meaningfully enhance students' writing.
Hartmeyer, R., Stevenson, M., & Bentsen, P. (2017). A systematic review of concept mapping-based formative assessment processes in primary and secondary science education. <i>Assessment in Education, Principles, Policy & Practice</i> , 25(6), 598-619.	9	n/a	Concept mapping-based interventions in science education [Middle & upper primary/secondary]	All studies report positive results, e.g., positive cognitive outcomes for students; improved achievement; improved student reasoning; positive outcomes for teachers Low-directed concept mapping (i.e., minimal guidance from teacher) appears to be an effective method for eliciting students' understanding; some evidence that concept mapping constructed and/or revised, and assessed in teaching is advantageous. Individually constructed concept mapping elicits personal understanding, while collaborative concept mapping highlighted as fostering understanding through meaningful negotiation with peers. Processes of concept mapping-embedded formative assessment differed greatly between the studies.
Heitink, M. C., van der Kleij, F., Veldkamp, B. P., Schildkamp, K., & Kippers, W. B. (2016). A systematic review of prerequisites for implementing assessment for learning in classroom practice. <i>Educational Research Review</i> , 17, 50-62.	25	n/a	Prerequisites for implementation of Assessment for Learning [4-18 years]	Prerequisites grouped under 'teacher', 'student', 'assessment' and 'school context' (not discrete): - teachers' knowledge and skills; beliefs and attitudes; constructivist approach to pedagogy - provision of assessment criteria/training to students; student autonomy in learning and AfL process - substantial, constructive and focused feedback; alignment of AfL with curriculum and standards and integration of AfL with instruction; - supportive school leaders; school and classroom climate encompassing mutual trust/respect and teacher autonomy
Hodgen, J., Foster, C., Marks, R., & Brown, M. (2018). <i>Improving Mathematics in Key Stages Two and Three: Evidence Review</i> . London: Education Endowment Foundation	4 meta-analyses specifically focused on feedback and formative assessment. ¹	Qualitative descriptors of effects	Effect of giving feedback to learners in mathematics [9-14 years]	Feedback generally found to have large effects on learning Feedback should be clear, task-related and encourage effort; in general should be used sparingly and predominantly reserved for more complex tasks; literature on misconceptions in mathematics viewed as providing a fruitful framework to guide feedback. Computer-based formative assessment, and formative assessment based on PD appear to be more effective than other approaches to formative assessment.

Hodgen, J., Barclay, N., Foster, C., Gilmore, C., Marks, R. and Simms, V. (2020). <i>Early Years and Key Stage 1 Mathematics Teaching: Evidence Review</i> . London: Education Endowment Foundation.	6 studies specifically focused on feedback and formative assessment ²	0.31	Effect of formative assessment and feedback on children's mathematical learning [3-7 years]	Effects found to be positive but evidence weak to moderate for this age group; observation, interviews, documentation of children's talk, collation of work samples, tasks and interviews promoted in best evidence syntheses and expert reviews of research; teachers' understanding of developmental progression facilitates use of assessment; some indications that computer-based tools can support formative assessment; some evidence supporting use of corrective feedback on accuracy in number fact recall and problem solving but should be combined with opportunity for children to engage conceptually with mathematics. Formative assessment should be part of wide-ranging teaching practices.
Kingston, N., & Nash, B. (2011). Formative assessment: A meta-analysis and call for research. <i>Educational Measurement: Issues and Practice</i> , 30(4), 28-37.	13 studies and 42 independent effect sizes.	0.25	Effect of formative assessment on educational achievement [K-12]	Two types of implementation of formative assessment, one based on professional development and the other on the use of computer-based formative systems, appeared to be more effective than other approaches, yielding mean effect size of .30 and .28, respectively. Moderator analyses indicated that formative assessment might be more effective in English language arts (ELA) than in mathematics or science, with estimated effect sizes of .32, .17, and .09, respectively. Two types of implementation of formative assessment, one based on professional development and the other on the use of computer-based formative systems, appeared to be more effective than other approaches, yielding mean effect size of .30 and .28, respectively (those this also related to the lack of high quality studies available in areas such as curriculum-based assessment, and specific use of student feedback). A call for more high-quality research studies on the effects of formative assessment was issued by the authors.
Klute, M., Apthorp, H., Harlacher, J., & Reale, M. (2017). <i>Formative assessment and elementary school student academic achievement: A review of the evidence</i> (REL 2017-259). U.S. Department of	23	0.26	Effect of formative assessment on academic achievement [Elementary]	Very small number of studies in K-3 grades. Formative assessment (in interventions of four weeks or less) found to have a positive impact on academic achievement - effect size greater for mathematics (0.36) than for reading (0.22) or writing (0.21). Across all studies student-directed formative assessment found to have less impact than other-directed formative assessment; in mathematics both student-directed and other-directed formative assessment effective; other-directed more beneficial for reading; insufficient evidence on effect of student-directed formative assessment on writing.

Education, Institute of Education Sciences, National Center for Education Evaluation and Regional Assistance, Regional Educational Laboratory Central.				
*Lane, R, Parrila, R, Bower, M, Bull, R, Cavanagh, M, Forbes, A, Jones, T, Leaper, D, Khosronejad, M, Pellicano, L, Powell, S, Ryan, M, & Skrebneva, I. (2019). <i>Formative assessment evidence and practice literature review</i> . Australian Curriculum and Assessment Reporting Authority, Educator Services Australia, and the Australian Institute for Teaching and School Leadership.	71	n/a	Effective formative assessment practices of teachers and school leaders [K-12]	<p>Studies show a small number of yearly assessment points is not sufficient in providing timely feedback to students on specific learning tasks. Frequent and embedded formative feedback may be critical to effective implementation of formative assessment practices. Studies in which formative assessments were followed by evidence-based interventions tended to produce better results.</p> <p>The general principles for the effective application of formative assessment employment were found to apply to online assessment. Basing online assessments on a valid model of task components and the prerequisite cognitive and learning skills underlying successful progression was deemed crucial. It was concluded that interventions need to be evidence-based and aligned with validated learning progressions for the targeted concept or skill. A list of effective features of professional development for formative assessment is provided (Chapter 8).</p> <p>24 (maths), 20 (online maths), 15 (reading), 5 (writing), Arts (2 - adjusted search to locate some qualitative studies)</p>
Lee, H., Chung, H.Q., Zhang, Y., Abedi, J., & Warschauer, M. (2020). The effectiveness and features of formative assessment in US K-12 education: A systematic review. <i>Applied Measurement</i>	33	0 .29 (effect on learning); 0.61 (features)	Impact of formative assessment on student learning; features of effective formative assessment [K-12]	<p>Overall small-sized positive effect of formative assessment on student learning Effect higher for literacy (0.33), mathematics (0.34), arts (0.29) than for science (0 .13). Formative assessment interventions most effective when focused on providing student-initiated formative assessments - empirical evidence supporting the cognitive and constructivist view of learning for formative assessment, where learners' active role is considered essential to successful formative assessment. Formal formative assessment found to be more effective than informal formative assessment; medium-cycle length more advantageous than short-cycle length; formative assessment interventions with the planned instructional adjustment component were effective in promoting student</p>

<i>in Education, 33(2), 124-140.</i>				learning outcomes; evidence supporting need for professional development and ongoing support for teachers; dynamic interaction of these identified features of formative assessment interventions highlighted.
Looney, A. (2019). <i>Digital formative assessment: A review of the literature.</i> assess@learning	200	n/a	Digital formative assessment [K-12]	Literature review of formative digital assessment in this EU-sponsored report. Useful definition of digital formative assessment (DFA) is provided, alongside a framework for evaluating DFA that incorporates the learning environment, student-centred learning and assessment, and collaborative learning and assessment. The body of the report is primarily description, with overviews of recent developments in digital assessment drawing on such tools as student e-portfolios, social media, digital textbooks, mobile learning, classroom polling, digital games and integrated formative and summative assessment. The paper concludes with some broad implications for research and policy, including teacher education, teacher development, coherence of digital formative assessment with other educational priorities, accessibility of digital tools and programmes, implications for equity, and encouraging investment in research and development.
Newman, M., Kwan, I., Shucan Bird, K., Hoo, H.T. (2021). <i>The impact of feedback on student attainment: a systematic review.</i> Education Endowment Foundation.	51	0.17	Impact of feedback [5-18 years]	Meta-syntheses have reported positive impacts of feedback for student achievement at different stages of education and have been influential in establishing feedback as an effective strategy to support student learning. The review arises from a concern that previous syntheses have combined studies of a variety of different feedback approaches, or where feedback is one of a number of intervention components, with several methodological limitations (for example, the lack of quality appraisal of the included studies). Feedback to individual students was reported in 48 studies and feedback to group or class is reported in four studies. Subgroup analyses focused on characteristics of the feedback, the educational setting, the learners and the subject. Because of statistically significant heterogeneity associated with subgroup effects, the authors concluded that a variety of student and context factors may have an effect on the impact of feedback.
Nikou & Economides, 2018 Mobile-based assessment: A literature review of publications in major refereed journals from 2009 to 2018. <i>Computers & Education, 125</i> , 101-119.	43	n/a	Impact of mobile-based assessment on student learning [Elementary, secondary, tertiary]	Most of the reviewed articles were conducted in four specific country contexts: Taiwan (28%), China (14%), USA (9%) and Spain (9%). The participants are elementary schools students (30%), followed by University students (28%) and students in secondary education (23%), while 9% of the studies involve a mixed population of both teachers and students (primarily from tertiary education). The articles were drawn from 7 journals. Almost half of the articles were Science (Physics, Information Technology, Environmental education) and Mathematics related subjects (49%). Sixty percent of studies reported positive effects on learning, 2% reported negative effects, 33% did not

				specify effects, and 5% were reported to be neutral. Over one-third of studies (35%) were reported to have had a positive effect on student motivation, while (72%) reported positive student attitudes and perceptions about mobile-based assessment.
Sanchez, C. E., Atkinson, K. M., Koenka, A. C., Moshontz, H., & Cooper, H. (2017). Self-grading and peer-grading for formative and summative assessments in 3rd through 12th grade classrooms: A meta-analysis. <i>Journal of Educational Psychology, 109</i> (8), 1049–1066.	33	0.34	Effects of self-grading and peer-grading practices [Primary/secondary]	Both self-grading and peer-grading (SPG) positively affected subsequent achievement/performance, with self-grading showing a larger positive long-term effect. In most cases students were trained and used rubrics. More studies investigated the effect of SPG as formative assessment rather than summative assessment. No significant difference in effect sizes for studies with younger compared with older students; no significant effect of self-grading outcomes for STEM classes compared with other subjects; no significant effect of students receiving one type of training or receiving multiple types of training; no significant effect found for frequency of self-grading exposure on subsequent tests. Students in fifth to 12th grades evaluated students' tests similarly to teachers - in both grades assigned and the distribution of grades.
Schildkamp, K., van der Kleij, F.M., Heitink, M.C., Kippers, W.B., & Veldkamp, B.P. (2020). Formative assessment: A systematic review of critical teacher prerequisites for classroom practice. <i>International Journal of Educational Research, 50</i> -62	54	n/a	Teacher prerequisites for using formative assessment [Primary/secondary]	Two approaches to formative assessment identified: Data-Based Decision Making (DBDM) and Assessment for Learning (AfL); Data literacy important for DBDM; assessment literacy important for AfL; Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) required to implement DBDM and AfL; goal setting can promote use of DBDM (at level of school, classroom or individual student) and AfL (student learning goals); for both DBDM and AfL- ICT skills, collaboration between teachers, positive attitude and ownership over results are key; involvement of students highlighted (predominantly AfL studies); high-quality feedback and facilitation of classroom discussion important for AfL; in DBDM studies, data use often linked to accountability and high stakes testing, and not to improvement; curricular constraints can hinder use of AfL.
See, B. H., Gorard, S., Lu, B., Dong, L., & Siddiqui, N. (2021). Is technology always helpful?: A critical review of the impact on learning outcomes of	56	n/a	Impact of digitally delivered formative assessment on learning outcomes [K-12]	While the authors reported that there was promising evidence that digitally delivered formative assessment could facilitate the learning of maths and reading for young children, they found limited or no evidence for other subjects, or for older children, or that formative assessment with technology was any more effective than formative assessment without technology. The review found no good evidence that learner response systems work in enhancing children's academic attainment, and no evidence

education technology in supporting formative assessment in schools, <i>Research Papers in Education</i>				was found to support the effectiveness of technologies that embed gaming features. A key feature of the article is the critical stance towards studies adopted by the authors, and this is evidenced in their rating of each study they reviewed, based on its quality. Only studies awarded a 2 or 3 (none was awarded a 4) are described in the article. Just 22 such studies were reviewed. In general, this study is less optimistic than, for example, Looney (2019) in describing the possibilities of technology to offer effective digital formative assessment.
Van der Kleij, F.M., Feskens, R.C.W., & Eggen, T.H.M. (2015). Effects of feedback in a computer-based learning environment on students' learning outcomes: A meta-analysis. <i>Review of Educational Research</i> , 85(4), 475-511.	40	n/a	Effects of feedback in a computer-based learning environment on students' learning outcomes [K-12]	Focused on the effects of feedback in a computer-based environment (essentially, the nature of feedback on test items completed on computer in various subject areas). Elaborated feedback (e.g., providing an explanation) produced larger effect sizes (0.49) than feedback regarding the correctness of the answer (0.05) or providing the correct answer (0.32). Effect sizes were positively affected by elaborated feedback, and larger effect sizes were found for mathematics compared with social sciences, science, and languages. Although the results suggested that immediate feedback was more effective for lower order learning than delayed feedback and vice versa, no significant interaction was found. Literature review contains a good overview of the nature and effects of feedback in formative assessment.
Yan, Z.; Li, Z.; Panadero, E.; Yang, M.; Yang, L.; Lao, H. (2021). A systematic review on factors influencing teachers' intentions and implementations regarding formative assessment. <i>Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice</i> , 28(3), 228-260.	52	n/a	Factors influencing teachers' intentions to implement formative assessment [Pre-primary to tertiary]	The major personal factors influencing teachers' intentions to conduct formative assessment were instrumental attitude, self-efficacy, and education and training. The widely reported contextual factors included internal school support, external policy, school environment, and cultural norm. For implementation, education and training, instrumental attitude, and teacher beliefs were the most common personal factors, with school environment, internal school support, and working conditions as the most frequently reported contextual factors. The meso-factors of internal school support and school environment were identified as two of the top three influential factors for both teachers' intentions and implementations. Just two studies looked at the interaction between teacher intentions and implementations regarding formative assessment.

¹ The purpose of the review was to synthesise the best available international evidence regarding teaching mathematics to children between the ages of 9 and 14. It included a focus on formative assessment. In all there were 66 meta-analyses + 22 narrative reviews across a range of topics.

² The purpose of the review was to synthesise the best available international evidence regarding teaching (and assessment) of mathematics to children at Key Stage 1 in England. It included a focus on formative assessment.

